

Milestone MS2

**Decision on the EOVs to be
used as a pilot and
identification of the available
datasets**

MILESTONE

Milestone	MS2 Decide on a well-defined EOV to be used as a pilot and identify available datasets
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1. Introduction

1.1 About the agreed EOVS and available data sets milestone report

This milestone is a report on the preparation process for the decision on the Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) to be used as a pilot in the ObsSea4Clim project and on identifying the available datasets. An adequate amount of data is a prerequisite to train any Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning (AI/ML) model to perform well a desired task and the choice of a pilot EOVS could depend primarily on that. However, by involving the consortium partners in this decision with an internal survey, we have achieved the following:

- agree on a pilot EOVS that is also fit-for-purpose for a number of ObsSea4Clim partners' needs,
- test on an additional second variable and ensure consistency in EOVS of interest throughout the project,
- focus on testing the AI/ML algorithms in a smaller region, since the global scale approach will pose serious computational limitations.

Furthermore, since the performance of the AI/ML models depends on the data used to train them, the data availability of the EOVS of interest is also considered and the partners' feedback on this was also requested. This report briefly explains the rationale behind the choice of the pilot EOVS based on the literature and more importantly, based on the partners' contribution, which has been provided through a feedback questionnaire..

1.2 Means of Verification

The means of verification according to the Description of Action is the list of agreed pilot EOVS to be used in Task 2.3. This list is provided in Table 1, on section 3 of this report and is the result of current literature review (section 2.1) in combination with feedback provided from the ObsSea4Clim partners (section 2.2) through the questionnaire in Annex 1.

2. Agreed pilot EOVS and available data sets

2.1 Pilot EOVS for Uncertainty quantification of EOVS/ECV using AI/ML algorithms

The need for sustainable ocean measurements, that are not only collected following the Ocean Best Practice guidelines but are also simultaneously evaluated based on an overall scientific consensus depending on the variable, has led to the development of the concept of the Essential Ocean Variables (Framework for Ocean Observing –FOO, Lindstrom et al., 2012). The Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) is responsible for identifying those variables that are important for describing and studying the ocean under ever-changing observing conditions¹. The list of EOVS that is available by GOOS is evolving as new scientific questions related to ocean conditions become important enough to increase the impact of an ocean variable. For the case of ECVs, the list of variables is monitored by the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) organization (sponsored by the World Meteorological Organization - WMO). The ECV list contains variables that are essential in order to describe and monitor the earth's climate, and

¹ <https://goosiocean.org/what-we-do/framework/essential-ocean-variables/>

these also include land and atmosphere-related variables in addition to the ocean variables, which for the most part coincide with the EOVs².

By definition, to be able to accurately report a measurement of any variable, the uncertainty of the measurement needs to be known (JCGM, 2008). Therefore, the value of an EOV x_{EOV} should be reported as: $x_{EOV} = x_{measured} \pm \Delta x$, where $x_{measured}$ is the actual measurement value as recorded by the instrumentation and Δx is the uncertainty associated with the measurement and includes uncertainties for example due to the instrumentation itself or due to statistical errors. The knowledge of the uncertainties is a complex issue since it is highly dependent on the conditions that a measurement is taken (e.g. instrumentation, possible biases etc.). This makes it challenging to accurately report EOV values, without referring to these exact conditions. In that context, the most accurate EOVs are the ones that are most studied, and for which an adequate amount of research has been performed in defining their uncertainties. Ocean temperature (surface and subsurface) is the EOV/ECV that most scientific research has been focused on with a few studies that explicitly focus on quantifying ocean temperature associated uncertainties (Cowley et al., 2021; Waldmann et al, 2022). Additionally, ocean temperature is thus far the preferred EOV used to test algorithms and methods that are used to automatically quality control data (Mieruch et al., 2021; Castelao, 2021; Good et al., 2023) and the process of quality control and uncertainty quantification are closely linked: without the uncertainty the quality assessment of a value is at best a qualitative description. Based on the above-mentioned studies, ocean temperature (surface and/or subsurface) is a safe choice as a pilot EOV for Task 2.3, which this report is linked to.

The data set availability for AI/ML algorithm implementation is another key point that needs to be considered. Temperature is by far the EOV that has been recorded the

² <https://gcos.wmo.int/en/essential-climate-variables/>

most, both from in-situ and satellite measurements. Most ocean observing platforms have been collecting temperature measurements (bottle samples and CTD profiles from research vessels, Argo floats, gliders, XBTs, drifters, moored buoys, ferrybox systems) since the early 1900s and satellites have been accurately measuring sea surface temperatures since the early 1990s. For example, in the World Ocean Database, the largest number of profiles per variable are the ones for temperature (1.95 billion profiles in the WOD2018 version) (Boyer et al, 2008). Therefore, from a data availability perspective, ocean temperature is again a safe choice for the needs of Task 2.3.

In terms of where the temperature data to be used will be provided from, the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS)³, in combination with the World Ocean Database (WOD)⁴ should cover the needs of the task. CMEMS provides in situ, satellite and numerical model outputs (reanalysis and forecast) data for blue, white and green ocean on a global and regional scales and for an extensive set of variables (physical and biogeochemical). However, for the majority of CMEMS satellite⁵ and in situ products,⁶ data spans from the mid-1980s to today, as a consequence any insights gained from older measurements during the training process of the AI/ML algorithms will be lost. The WOD database is expected to complement the CMEMS data, especially when including historical data, to accurately incorporate the EOVS temporal variability in the AI/ML approach.

2.2 Collecting inputs from the ObsSea4Clim work packages

In a collaborative effort between Tasks 2.3 and 2.4 (led by HCMR and ETT respectively), a questionnaire was drafted to identify which is/are the more fit-for-purpose EOVS/ECVs relevant to the project. The questionnaire is attached as Annex 1. The questionnaire was

³ <https://gcos.wmo.int/en/essential-climate-variables/>

⁴ <https://gcos.wmo.int/en/essential-climate-variables/>

⁵ <https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/products?facets=sources%7ESatellite+observations>

⁶ <https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/products?facets=sources%7EIn-situ+observations>

sent to all the work packages and the replies related to Task 2.3 have been then digested in this milestone report. A total of 15 partners replied to the questionnaire, with major involvement in work packages 2, 3 and 4 which are mainly users of oceanographic observations (Figure 1).

Fig. 1: Questionnaire replies per work package of ObsSea4Clim.

2.2.1 EOV/ECV of interest

On the first question of the questionnaire (Annex 1), the partners were asked “*which EOV/ECV should be used according to your knowledge, expertise and project needs*”. The answers are summarized in Figure 2. While the majority of the partners are interested in the **SST** and **subsurface ocean temperature**, partners are also interested in testing the AI/ML approach on **ocean currents** as well. This will be taken into consideration depending on the time of completion of the next step related to Task 2.3 (i.e. choice of the AI/ML algorithm, MS7). The advantage of choosing SST over

subsurface temperature is the fact that satellite data is available for the sea surface, providing excellent spatial coverage but for a shorter period of time, in comparison to in-situ temperature observations (see also 2.1)^{7,8}. Temperature (SST and subsurface) are both more scientifically mature for studies similar to the ones related to Task 2.3 (relevant publications in section 2.1) and additionally, are both almost equally important to partners. Hence, the AI/ML approach will be tested on **SST** first and then on **subsurface ocean temperature**. The surface ocean currents EO/ECV could also be considered depending on the timeliness of Task’s 2.3 actions execution. The decision to test on surface ocean currents, instead of subsurface ocean currents, is a choice that is based on the fact that there are satellite measurements of surface ocean currents⁹, increasing the data availability for testing this EO/ECV.

Fig. 2: Summary of the partner-suggested EO/ECVs from the questionnaire (Annex 1). SST: Sea Surface Temperature, T(sub): subsurface ocean temperature, T(sea ice): sea ice temperature, SSS: SeaSurface Salinity, S: subsurface salinity, C(sea ice): sea ice concentration, SSH: Sea Surface

⁷ <https://goosocean.org/document/17466>

⁸ <https://goosocean.org/document/17467>

⁹ <https://goosocean.org/document/17468>

Height, U(surf): surface currents, U(sub): subsurface currents, the rest of the suggested variables don't have an abbreviation on the figure.

2.2.2 Regional approach

The partners in the second part of the questionnaire (Annex 1, “Geographical Boundaries/Regional approach”) were asked to provide some feedback regarding the region which the AI/ML algorithms could be tested first. From Figure 3, there seems to be a preference for the Mediterranean Sea region, which reflects some of the scientific interests of WPs 3 and 4 (for example Mediterranean Marine Heat waves). At a closer look on Figure 3 though, the partners are overall mostly interested in the North Atlantic and Arctic region. This is a rather interesting result, as in principle the data availability of oceanographic measurements in the North Atlantic and Arctic areas is lower than in the Mediterranean mainly due to the difficulty of collecting data in this environment. Consequently, both the **Mediterranean** and the **North Atlantic-Arctic** regions are good candidates for AI/ML algorithm testing. The goal for the next steps of Task 2.3 will be to start testing on both and highlight the differences, similarities and algorithm performance at different regions with differences in data coverage.

Fig. 3: Regions of interest to the ObsSea4Clim partners

■ 2.2.3 Dataset preferences

In the “Data Selection and Methods” part of the questionnaire (Annex 1), the partners were asked to provide some input on the data sets they are using (or planning to use) as part of their ObsSea4Clim involvement (Question 3). Their answers are shown in Figure 4. The spread of the answers was expected as: (1) there are different scientific questions addressed in the project and (2) the data is how a scientific question can be addressed and there is no straightforward way of doing so, hence there could be numerous data sets used to answer even the same question. There is a preference by the partners to use the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS) data, however, as described in section 2.1, the WOD Database is also very useful for Task 2.3. Therefore, both the CMEMS Service and WOD Database will be used for testing the AI/ML uncertainty quantification methods.

Fig. 4: Partner data set preferences. CMEMS: Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service, SEANOE: SEA sciNtific Open data Edition, ODATIS: Ocean Data Information and Services, ESM: Earth System Model, NOAA: National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, CMIP6: Coupled Model Intercomparison Projects 6, OSI-SAF: Ocean and Sea Ice Satellite Application Facilities, C3S: Copernicus Climate Change Service.

3. Decisions on pilot EOVS and available data sets

Below is a summary table with the decisions described in this milestone report.

Agreed on Pilot EOVS	Proposed data sets	Regional Approach
SST	CMEMS, WOD	Mediterranean Sea
Subsurface ocean temperature	CMEMS, WOD	North Atlantic-Arctic
Surface Ocean Currents	CMEMS, WOD	

Table 1: Summary table of the decisions of the milestone report

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Annex 1: ObsSea4Clim questionnaire for EOVs/ECVs decision-making

Variables

Question 1:

An EOV/ECV will be chosen as a pilot to

- (a) evaluate the quality control of the variables using machine learning uncertainty quantification methods;
- (b) identify data gaps and data accuracy.

Which EOV/ECV should be used according to your knowledge, expertise and project needs?

List (briefly) the reasons for your choice (2-3 sentences max).

Geographical boundaries/ Regional approach

Question 1:

In the process of selecting an EOV/ECV, **please specify your preference regarding the area of interest?** (eg. Mediterranean Sea, Arctic, ...)

Question 2:

Scalability of the AI QC approach: The approach will be tested on a smaller scale (sub-regional to regional, i.e. Eastern Mediterranean expanded to the whole Mediterranean basin).

List the reasons why you think the approach should be tested on a specific area first (2-3 sentences max).

Data selection and methods

Question 1:

In order to effectively filter out data for scientific analysis, it's important to have the most complete metadata associated with the data.

What are the keywords and information that you use to filter data (eg. programme name, ship name, providing institute, observation program, sensor accuracy, QC/QF,...

Specify the keywords and sort the list by order of relevance)?

Instruction: up to 10 keywords, separated by a comma.

Question 2:

Data Quality is a complex issue.

How do you check or assess the quality of data? (2-3 sentences max)

Is the Quality Flag enough?

Do you need a link to the Quality Check methodology (paper/Best Practice) back to back to the Quality Flag?

Could a flag on the comparability of methodologies help when aggregating data from different sources? (check box: yes, no)

Question 3:

In order to effectively map the gaps that we currently have in marine environmental data, it's essential to understand the pathways of data sharing/interoperability towards the national and international aggregators.

Please list in which database and data assembly centre your data is available (from the institute to the international database) and indicate if data receive any further QC/QF or processing level in this database (the interest is to understand if different databases redistribute the original version of the data or if they are applying any processing). (free)

Question 4:

In an effort to consider all of our partners' prior, ongoing and future work related to the use of AI/ML methods within the project's thematic, please answer whether you are planning to use AI/ML methods in your project-related task.

Can you provide a short description (why, what, how 3-4 sentences)?

